

Luis Patricio Tierra Pérez, Ángel Patricio Flores Orozco, Rogelio Estalin Ureta Valdez, Patricio Vladimir Méndez Zambrano & Implementation Of Ict In The Environmental Conservation Teaching Process

IMPLEMENTATION OF ICT IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION TEACHING PROCESS

¹Luis Patricio Tierra Pérez; patricio.tierra@esPOCH.edu.ec; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3366-7867>

²Ángel Patricio Flores Orozco; angel.flores@esPOCH.edu.ec; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1484-2949>

³Rogelio Estalin Ureta Valdez; rogelio.ureta@esPOCH.edu.ec; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8756-8982>

⁴Patricio Vladimir Méndez Zambrano; patricio.mendez@esPOCH.edu.ec; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4305-8152>

^{1,2,3,4} Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo, Sede Morona Santiago, Macas EC140101, Ecuador

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Abstract

A documentary review was carried out on the production and publication of research papers related to studying the Teaching Process, ICT Inclusion and Environmental Conservation variables. The bibliometric analysis proposed in this paper was to know the main characteristics of the volume of publications registered in the Scopus database during 2017-2021, identifying 12 publications. The information provided by the said platform was organized employing tables and figures categorizing the information by Year of Publication, Country of Origin, Area of Knowledge and Type of Publication. Once these characteristics were described, a qualitative analysis was used to refer to the position of different authors on the proposed topic. Among the main findings of this research, it is found that Spain, with 3 publications, was the country with the highest scientific production registered in the name of authors affiliated with institutions of that country. The Area of Knowledge that made the most significant contribution to the construction of bibliographic material referring to the study of the implementation of ICT in the processes of Teaching for Environmental Conservation was Social Sciences with 8 published documents, and the Type of Publication that was most used during the above mentioned period was the Journal Article, representing 42% of the total scientific production.

Keywords: teaching process, inclusion of ict, environment

1. Introduction

In recent years, the concern about environmental conservation has become a topic of great importance worldwide, making a call for social interest and awareness for citizens, government agencies and governments worldwide. For this reason, different alternatives have been sought to emphasize solutions and thus develop an awareness of the various environmental problems caused by developing countries, industrialization and overexploitation of environmental resources.

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Likewise, the NGO aims to propose a new concept of sustainable development that takes into account the satisfaction of needs, the improvement of the quality of life and finally, a harmonious balance between humanity and nature; it is for this reason and for all the evidence that surrounds that people must change attitudes, before human greed, proposing environmental awareness and thus generate a great environmental impact, the preservation of the human species depends on the conservation of the planet. There are two elements of this great work: the family and education are responsible for generating respect for nature, forming ecological values, caring, and preserving the environment.

Education plays a fundamental role in the solution of this problem; the implementation of ICT plays an important role in the teaching process since it provides the means for the improvement of learning and, in turn, achieves comprehensive training for students, as well as the responsibility to generate in them, a change of awareness about attitudes, habits based on knowledge and the implementation of new ideas that help mitigate, provide and curb the actions of environmental degradation. For such reason, this article seeks to describe the main characteristics of the compendium of publications indexed in the Scopus database related to the variables Teaching Process, ICT Inclusion and Environmental Conservation, as well as the description of the position of certain authors affiliated to institutions, during the period between the years 2017 and 2021.

2. General Objective

To analyze from a bibliometric and bibliographic perspective, the production of research papers on the variables *ICT, teaching processes, and environmental conservation* was registered in Scopus during 2017-2021.

3. Methodology

Quantitative analysis of the information provided by Scopus under a bibliometric approach on the scientific production related to the study of Trends in Architecture in Latin America is carried out. Also, from a qualitative perspective, examples of some research papers published in the area of the study mentioned above are analyzed from a bibliographic approach to describe the position of different authors on the proposed topic.

The search is performed through the tool provided by Scopus, and the parameters referenced in Figure 1 are established.

3.1 Methodological design

Figure 1. Methodological design
Source: Own elaboration

3.1.1 Phase 1: Data Collection

The data collection was carried out using the Scopus web page search tool, through which a total of 12 publications were identified. For this purpose, search filters were established consisting of:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (teaching AND process, AND inclusion AND of AND ict, AND environment) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017)))

- ✓ Published papers whose study variables are related to the study of the implementation of ICT in teaching processes for environmental conservation.
- ✓ Without distinction of country of origin.
- ✓ Without distinction of area of knowledge.
- ✓ Without distinction of type of publication.

3.1.2 Phase 2: Construction of analysis material

The information identified in the previous phase is organized. The classification will be made employing graphs, figures and tables based on data provided by Scopus.

- ✓ Year of publication
- ✓ Country of origin of the publication.
- ✓ Knowledge area.
- ✓ Type of Publication
- ✓

3.1.3 Phase 3: Drafting conclusions and final document

After the analysis carried out in the previous phase, the study proceeded to draft the conclusions and results.

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4.1 Co-occurrence of words

Figure 2 shows the co-occurrence of keywords found in the publications identified in the Scopus database.

Figure 2. Co-occurrence of words

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data exported from Scopus.

The study of the research was reported by the Scopus platform, referring to the variables of the *Teaching Process, Inclusion of ICT and Environmental Conservation*. The object of this scientific debt is the importance of environmental conservation and the proper implementation of ICT in the teaching process since it provides the means for the improvement of learning and, in turn, implements educational strategies that seek to raise collective awareness for the care of our planet. It is for this reason that through the interpretation of Figure 2, it is possible to determine as keywords of the publications reported in Scopus, Education, Students, Computer-Assisted Instruction, and Teaching, in attention to the marked global concern for environmental conservation due to the different climatic factors, environmental deforestation and exploitation of environmental resources. In this same sense and according to the interpreted graph, words such as Inclusion, Information and Education, and Personal Training are of recurrent appearance in the works under analysis since, although the importance of natural resources and environmental conservation has indeed become an international interest, it has become necessary to implement policies that help mitigate climate change and achieve citizen awareness for the care of the planet.

4.2 Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.

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Figure 3 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the year of publication.

Figure 3. *Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.*
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data exported from Scopus.

Figure 3 shows the scientific production around the variables Teaching Process, ICT Inclusion and Environmental Conservation in the period between 2017 and 2022, where a decrease in production volume is evidenced in 2021, with a total of 2 publications related to the keywords, among which the article entitled “Impact on the virtual learning environment by covid-19” stands out (Martín et al., 2021), whose scope of the study was to know the perception that students of the Faculty of Education Sciences of the University of Granada have about the pedagogical model adopted in the virtual learning environment during the confinement until the second semester of the course 2019-2020. The data collection method was an online questionnaire using simple random sampling with a proportional affix of 0.5, a 95% confidence level and a maximum permissible error of 4.7%. The results show a generalized dissatisfaction among the students being fundamental to carrying out the transition of the educational and teacher training processes. The implementation of active methodologies increases due to the virtual condition, specifically the inverted classroom methodology, but students manifest a generalized dissatisfaction regarding the adequate methodological development and the involvement of teachers. The use of e-mail and the virtual learning platform (PRADO) stands out, although they consider that they do not have adequate knowledge about image editors, video, infographics, synchronous response systems and anti-plagiarism tools.

4.3 Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the nationality of the authors.

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Figure 4. *Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.*
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Spain had the highest number of publications registered in Scopus referring to the study of the variable Teaching Process, ICT Inclusion and Environmental Conservation. During the period 2017-2021, with a total of 3 publications, followed by Kazakhstan with 2 registrations and Sweden with 1. Of the latter, the article entitled “Foresight as a tool to increase creativity in the era of technology-enhanced learning” stands out (Woodgate, 2018), whose study objective is the inclusion of established foresight science methodologies within the structure of an ICT course can lead to higher levels of student creativity when these processes are learned through a multimedia-enhanced learning environment. This framework took advantage of the unique characteristics of foresight science as it seeks to determine and create future opportunities in any specific domain. This provided the opportunity to engage each student in the ultimate resolution of potential future real-life problems by learning methodologies and techniques for alternative thinking in a plausible future scenario full of unknowns and to develop novel multimedia approaches and tools for the future of mobile learning, which placed considerable emphasis on developing cognitive and physical creative skills and allowed them to experience the current and emerging challenges of mobile learning. Consequently, the final project for the students involved the creation of a fully structured project thesis demonstrating how emerging multimedia could provide future content for a mobile learning course curriculum that he or she had designed and considered would be prominent in 2030.

4.4 Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the production of scientific publications according to the area of knowledge through which the different research methodologies are implemented.

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Figure 5. *Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge.*
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Social Sciences was the area of knowledge with the highest number of publications registered in Scopus, with 8 documents that have based their methodologies on the variable Teaching Process, ICT Inclusion and Environmental Conservation. In the second place, Communication Sciences with 6 documents. Of the above, the article with the greatest impact was registered in the area of Social Sciences entitled “Key competencies, education for sustainable development and strategies for the development of 21st century skills: A systematic review of the literature” (González-salamanca et al., 2020). This article aims to learn the design principles involved in incorporating these skills into the curriculum, discover possible ways to teach and assess them, and examine how this process could be customized using Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). A literature review was conducted through a qualitative meta-synthesis, in which 43 studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria. From the in-depth analysis, it can be seen that although the incorporation of 21st century skills in the curriculum, teaching methodologies and the use of ICTs are recurring themes, further research is still needed in the design and implementation of new assessment tools and ways to personalize the teaching-learning process.

4.5 Type of publication

The following graph (Figure 6) shows the distribution of the bibliographic findings according to the type of publication made by each of the authors found in Scopus.

Figure 6. Type of publication

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

The type of publication most frequently used by researchers was the Article; 41% of the total scientific production corresponds to this type of document. In the second place, Session Papers with 42% and Book Chapters with 17%. This last category includes the article entitled “An Educational Path on Universal Design: Video games as learning tools” (Buratti et al., 2021). This article focuses on PUDCAD (Practicing Universal Design Principles In Design Education Through A Cad-Based Game), a project funded by the European Erasmus program for innovation and exchange of good practices in education. PUDCAD aims to create a playful computer-aided drawing application that allows architects and interior design students to learn and use universal design principles. This article explains the different stages of the research implementation, and reviewing the process followed to build the application, the article explores the educational experimentation and pedagogical aspects, emphasizing how the video game, beyond entertainment, can support and promote new learning paths complementary to canonical teaching methods.

5. Conclusions

The implementation of ICTs positively enhanced the teaching-learning process and the reflection and awareness of environmental problems. Using different resources such as educational videos and different learning activities caused reflective changes in the teaching model, strengthening, contextualization and reflection of students facing the multiple problems of climate change and the importance of environmental conservation.

Creative development in addressing environmental issues involves the academy and the entire community in general, encouraging activities in favor of environmental conservation and behavior that demonstrates a sense of belonging to the planet. This is achieved through the values of preservation and the due recognition that there is only one opportunity for change.

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When implemented, the use of ICTs in learning models on environmental conservation generated advantages over traditional learning models due to several factors such as the availability of computers and internet access, the students' liking for the implementation of technology in the learning process, the programming and implementation of pedagogical strategies for environmental awareness and reflection on sustainable development.

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